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Best practice guidelines for local operators and innovation developers

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Responsible Author(s)	Sara Altamore (APRE), Karolina Jurkiewicz (APRE)		
Contributor(s)			
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Executive Summary

This report presents a set of Best Practice Guidelines to support local operators and innovation developers in the development and implementation of regional bioeconomy strategies. The guidelines are the result of lessons learned from six pilot regions involved in the BIOMODEL4REGIONS project: Delta Region (Netherlands), Nitra Region (Slovakia), Normandy Region (France), Northern Sweden (Sweden), Tuscany Region (Italy), and Western Macedonia (Greece).

Structured across three pillars — Blueprints Development, Business Model Development, and Governance Development — the document provides practical insights for developing inclusive, resilient, and locally rooted bioeconomy strategies. Each section includes thematic best practices, “how-to” guidance, key questions for practitioners, and illustrative examples from the pilot regions.

The guidelines emphasize stakeholder engagement, co-creation, capacity building, place-based business model design, policy alignment, and transparent governance. By drawing from real regional experiences, this report enables other territories to replicate and adapt effective practices, scale innovation, and foster systemic transitions toward sustainable and circular bioeconomy.

1 INTRODUCTION

The purpose of these best practice guidelines is to provide local operators and innovation developers with a practical framework for designing and implementing bioeconomy strategies. Drawing from the experiences and examples of the six pilot regions involved in the BIOMODEL4REGIONS project and the six pilot regions—Delta Region (Netherlands), Nitra Region (Slovakia), Normandy Region (France), Northern Sweden (Sweden), Tuscany Region (Italy), and Western Macedonia (Greece)— the guidelines offer actionable insights to help stakeholders navigate the complexities of developing bio-based economy strategy blueprints. The final aim is to support the development of strategies both locally relevant and globally impactful.

The BIOMODEL4REGIONS project itself aims to promote the development of sustainable bioeconomy across regions, focusing on bio-based solutions that align with local strengths and priorities. Through collaboration across the six pilot regions, the project fosters the creation of innovative models and strategies that support the transition to a bio-based economy, with an emphasis on regional involvement and adaptability.

This document is organized into three key areas: **Blueprints Development**, **Business Model Development**, and **Governance Development**. Each of these areas is further divided into specific best practices, grouped into thematic families, and illustrated with examples from the six BIOMODEL4REGIONS pilot regions.

In the **Blueprints Development** section, the best practices focus on early and inclusive stakeholder engagement, capacity building, and establishing clear pathways from strategy to action. These practices ensure that strategies reflect regional needs and priorities while promoting accountability through defined roles, responsibilities, and timelines. The **Business Model Development** section emphasizes the importance of designing models that are tailored to the local context. By taking into account regional strengths, available resources, and socio-economic dynamics, these models ensure resilience, relevance, and long-term success. The **Governance Development** section highlights the need for effective governance structures that are inclusive, aligned with policy frameworks, and capable of supporting continuous communication and learning.

In conclusion, the best practices presented in this document offer a comprehensive approach to developing and implementing bioeconomy strategies. By emphasizing stakeholder involvement, context-specific business models, and strong governance systems, these practices provide the foundation for regions to successfully transition to sustainable, bio-based economies. The examples from the pilot regions demonstrate that these approaches can be adapted and applied across diverse contexts, ensuring both resilience and long-term viability in the development of bioeconomy initiatives.

2 METHODOLOGY

The development of these Best Practice Guidelines is grounded in a participatory, practice-oriented methodology designed to capture, systematize, and translate the experiences of the six BIOMODEL4REGIONS pilot regions into actionable insights. The approach combines data collection from a dedicated survey and thematic analysis of the “Six regional bio-based economy strategy blueprints” (D5.1) ensuring that the final output is both evidence-based and practically useful for local operators and innovation developers.

Data Collection and Sources

Primary data were collected through a structured survey distributed to the six pilot regions: Delta (NL), Nitra (SK), Normandy (FR), Northern Sweden (SE), Tuscany (IT), and Western Macedonia (GR). The survey included open-ended questions aimed at exploring strategies, operational processes, stakeholder dynamics, and governance arrangements adopted in the design and implementation of regional bioeconomy initiatives.

The survey addressed three core dimensions highlighted in the blueprints:

- Blueprint development processes, including co-creation, capacity building, and implementation roadmaps;
- Business model design, with attention to local anchoring, innovation, market alignment, and sustainability;
- Governance mechanisms, focusing on coordination, policy alignment, and transparency.

Complementary information was gathered through desk research (e.g. regional blueprints, action plans, workshop reports), and internal project exchanges. These multiple sources enhanced the robustness of the findings.

Analytical Process

Once collected, data were analysed through a thematic synthesis process. Responses were systematically reviewed and coded according to recurring patterns and innovative elements across the three key areas: blueprint, business model, and governance development. This allowed for the identification of clusters of practices and enabling conditions that were either common across regions or context-specific but potentially transferable.

Each best practice was formulated based on:

- A concise description of the practice;
- Operational guidance in “how-to” format;
- Key reflective questions for practitioners;
- Concrete regional examples illustrating the application of the practice in real settings.

This structure aims to support both strategic thinking and operational decision-making.

From Regional Experience to Practical Guidance

The final framework presented in this document is not a prescriptive model but rather a flexible tool that can be adapted to different regional contexts. By drawing from real-world practices and lessons learned across diverse bioeconomy ecosystems, the methodology bridges the gap between strategic planning and grounded implementation.

Ultimately, the process reflects the project’s core values of co-creation, mutual learning, and local empowerment — offering a replicable and scalable approach to support the transition toward sustainable, inclusive, and resilient bio-based economies.

3 BEST PRACTICES FOR BLUEPRINTS DEVELOPMENT

Developing effective bio-based economy strategy blueprints involves a diverse range of stakeholder engagement, structured communication, capacity building, and clear pathways from strategy to action. It starts with an **early and inclusive stakeholder engagement** to co-create strategy blueprint that reflect regional needs and priorities. **Capacity building and awareness-raising** initiatives support the process and equip local actors with the knowledge and skills to actively contribute and adopt bio-based solutions. In all phases, it's important to ensure **transparency** and define a **clear implementation pathway** – with roles, responsibilities, timelines, and monitoring tools – to turn strategic visions into coordinated and accountable actions. Below a focus on each subtopic.

3.1 STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT AND CO-CREATION

Stakeholder engagement is essential to align policy objectives with real-world implementation. Effective communication planning, structured follow-up, and co-creation activities are key to fostering a multi-actor approach. These practices ensure that regional strategies for bio-based transitions are co-owned and well-coordinated.

3.1.1 Best practice 1: Engage stakeholders from the beginning

Early and inclusive stakeholder engagement is crucial for ensuring that blueprints development effectively address regional needs. Participatory knowledge production enhances learning, trust, and ownership. Moreover, co-creative activities foster a multi-actor approach, aimed at strengthening the reliability, demand orientation, and societal relevance of research and innovation processes.

How to

- **Map stakeholders** early on using influence/interest grids or stakeholder matrices.
- Ensure **quadruple helix** representation: government, business, academia, and civil society.
- **Run pre-engagement surveys** to understand expectations, needs, and levels of awareness.
- **Clarify goals** for each activity – what is being decided or co-developed?
- Plan **targeted workshops** for different strategy phases (from building a shared vision, to design, prioritization, and validation).
- Choose the **appropriate method** based on your objective, such as Delphi surveys, participatory SWOT analysis, or co-design workshops.
- Remember to **not overload stakeholders** – avoid overlapping or repetitive topics and activities.

Key questions for practitioner:

What are the objectives I want to reach with my co-creative activity?

Who are the key stakeholders to involve that cover the quadruple helix?

How could efficiently involve diverse stakeholders to co-create knowledge and build shared ownership?

Do I consider existing networks of stakeholders?

Have I involved the right mix of stakeholders early enough to shape a shared vision?

What is the more appropriate way to combine diverse knowledge and experiences gained from the stakeholders?

Examples

- **Delta Region:** Early involvement was considered essential for ensuring an appropriate representation, higher number and quality of engagement. Over 40 stakeholders were actively engaged from the beginning through workshops and interviews to co-develop a common vision and strategy.
- **Northern Sweden:** Arrange workshops around the proposal and the referral proposal for the Swedish Bioeconomy strategy, allowing stakeholder input at multiple stages and further strengthening their cooperation.
- **Western Macedonia Region:** Applied Delphi-SWOT for structured expert consultation and reinforcing the importance of participatory decision-making.
- **Nitra Region:** Co-creation workshops promoted open dialogue across sectors.
- **Tuscany:** Cross-sector workshops supported knowledge exchange. The region adopted a quadruple helix approach, engaging key local actors to align the business models with existing agri-food systems and innovation ecosystems.

3.1.2 Best practice 2: Plan Communication & Follow-up

A transparent and structured communication process keeps stakeholders informed, committed, and aligned throughout implementation. It also ensures continuity and responsiveness.

How to

- Use both **in-person and online formats**, either alternately or in hybrid mode, to ensure accessibility and continuity.
- Build **feedback loops** into communications, e.g., surveys, summary reports, visual dashboards.
- Promote **two-way exchanges** between institutions and local actors.

Key questions for practitioner:

How will I ensure consistent and meaningful communication with stakeholders during and after strategy development?

What will be the purpose of communication with stakeholders?

What will be the more appropriate channels for communication with stakeholders?

What actionable messages I would like to share with the stakeholders?

Examples

- **Tuscany Region:** Used liaison offices and combination of multi-stakeholder structured dialogue and digital collaboration tools to coordinate between sectors and institutions.
- **Nitra Region:** Maintained continuous cross-sector feedback loops involving “quadruple helix” stakeholders, in particular municipalities, waste managers, farmers, and civil society.

3.2 CAPACITY BUILDING AND AWARENESS

Capacity building and awareness are essential elements in blueprint development because they empower stakeholders with the knowledge, skills, and shared understanding needed to actively contribute, adopt innovative solutions, and ensure long-term ownership and implementation of the strategy.

3.2.1 Best practice 3: prioritize education and building awareness in your process

Awareness and education are essential for successful implementation. An effective way to foster both is to integrate campaign into the blueprint development process and engage educational institutions, ensuring that all actors can contribute meaningfully.

How to

- Plan to insert and run **awareness campaigns** using different media during the process of blueprints development.
- **Engage for education institutions**, including schools for building education pathways and increasing knowledge on bio-based economy.
- Look for existing **digital knowledge platforms** for resource sharing.

Key questions for practitioner:

How am I enabling stakeholders to understand, support, and act on the building of a shared bio-based economy vision?

What do stakeholders already know about the bio-based economy?

What will be the objectives of the awareness raising activities (e.g., increase awareness, change stakeholder behaviour or attitudes, build capacity or understanding, etc.)?

What will be the educational and awareness raising methods and activities (e.g., workshops, seminars, webinars, social media, brochures, etc.)?

How can I monitor and track changes in stakeholder knowledge, attitude, and behaviour?

Examples:

- **Western Macedonia Region:** Ran training, campaigns, and outreach to support stakeholder readiness. Raising awareness through knowledge-sharing platforms, workshops, and digital resources ensured a broader understanding of bio-based economy potential and its economic, social, and environmental benefits. Consumer education and

incentives are needed to increase adoption and competitiveness of sustainable alternatives.

- **Delta Region:** Strengthened links with educational institutions for workforce readiness and expanded green economy training to support adaptation to technological and organizational change.
- **Nitra Region:** Promoted bio-based economy through public education linked to the Association of Municipalities for waste management in Nitra Region (PZO). In particular, the replicable model of innovative waste management (using the PZO model) was proposed and an education campaign started to engage the community through education.

3.2.2 Best practice 4: capacity building activities

Beyond awareness, deepening skills and operational capacity enables long-term regional transition. Enhanced capacity leads to better implementation and sustained progress towards regional bio-based economy goals.

How to

- **Assess capacity gaps** through feedback collected during stakeholder engagement.
- Map or monitor during co-creative activities **the needs for building training sessions** for different stakeholder groups (farmers, SMEs, public servants) to organize training aligned to needs.
- Design **modular training** sessions that address technical, governance, and entrepreneurial skills.
- Promote **peer learning** across regions or municipalities.

Key questions for practitioner:

What skills and knowledge are missing among key actors – and how can I support them to build that capacity?

What will be the objectives of the capacity building activities?

What will be the format of the capacity building activities (e.g., workshops, e-learning modules, mentoring, study tours, etc.)?

What will be the structure of the capacity building activities (e.g., modules, progressive levels, lectures, discussions, etc.)?

What will be the content of the capacity building activities?

Examples

- **Nitra and Western Macedonia Regions** specifically connected capacity building to replicable governance and business model implementation.
- **The Tuscany Region** highlighted capacity-building initiatives aimed at empowering municipalities and local stakeholders, as well as fostering circular practices, policies, and initiatives. In addition, mentorship schemes were planned to connect startups with industry leaders and academic experts.

3.3 DATA QUALITY AND IMPLEMENTATION PATHWAY

3.3.1 Best practice 5: Enhancing Data Quality and Information Flow

Ensuring a transparent flow of data and information between institutions and stakeholders is essential to support informed decision-making, enhance accountability, and monitor the progress of regional bio-based economy strategies over time.

How to

- **Identify key data gaps** such as biomass availability, waste flows, energy use, or socio-economic impacts.
- Develop or use existing and trustable **shared digital platforms** for collecting, analysing, and visualising data.
- Create **user-friendly reporting formats** to support understanding across different stakeholder groups (e.g., policymakers, citizens, funders).
- **Set up regular data-sharing routines** between municipalities, regional coordinators, and national agencies.

Key questions for practitioner:

Do I have reliable, shared bio-based economy data management systems (data collection, analytics, reporting) in place – and are stakeholders actively using them to guide decisions and improvements?

What are the key challenges and gaps in the current bio-based economy data management systems (e.g., statistical classifications, value chain data, need for regional data, etc.)?

What bio-based economy data management tools and platforms are available?

Which of the stakeholders are involved in the bio-based economy data management? What are their roles and responsibilities?

Examples

- **Delta Region:** Through the Circular Bio-Based Delta (CBBDD) initiative, the importance of selecting KPIs that are SMART (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound) raised for improving transparency.
- **Nitra Region:** Digital tools used to track and report waste management performance. For example, the national and local data systems (like RISO) to monitor waste flows and recycling rates. Key indicators (e.g., landfill diversion, biowaste separation targets) were tracked quarterly to guide strategy adjustments and support decision-making.

3.3.2 Best practice 6: Bridging Policy and Implementation

Bridging the gap between policy and implementation means turning long-term visions into concrete local actions that generate real impact. This requires developing process maps and implementation frameworks that support smooth collaboration between policymakers and local practitioners.

How to

- Develop **implementation roadmaps** with timelines, responsible actors, and funding links.
- Draft **roles & responsibilities guides** for institutions, municipalities, and communities.
- Consider to structure **task forces or liaison roles** for facilitating collaboration between policy and practice.
- **Monitor** and ensure that the regional bio-based economy strategy blueprint aligns with **national and European bio-based economy strategies** to promote policy coherence.

Key questions for practitioners:

How do I turn the regional bio-based economy vision into action – and who is responsible for doing what, by when?

How will this regional bio-based economy strategy blueprint align between regional, national, and European bio-based economy strategies to promote policy coherence and unlock funding opportunities?

Examples

- **Normandy, Delta, and Western Macedonia** Regions all addressed challenges in bridging high-level planning with practical implementation, suggesting clearer frameworks are key.

4 BEST PRACTICES FOR BUSINESS MODEL DEVELOPMENT

Best practices in business model development highlight the importance of designing **place-based models** that are deeply rooted in the local context. Regional strengths, available biomass, existing value chains, and socio-economic dynamics should all shape the model to ensure its relevance, resilience, and long-term viability. Success depends on **financial structures tailored to local realities**, supportive policies that foster cross-sector collaboration, and models that are both scalable and replicable. Moreover, a **market-driven approach** is crucial to ensure economic viability by aligning bioeconomy solutions with consumer demand, thereby securing long-term sustainability and broader impact.

4.1 PLACE-BASED DESIGN – BUSINESS MODELS ROOTED IN LOCAL REALITIES

Place-based design focuses on creating business models that are deeply rooted in and tailored to the unique characteristics and realities of local contexts. Business models that reflect the territorial specificities – available biomass, industrial structure, and socio-economic context – ensure long-term sustainability and reduce dependency on external inputs.

4.1.1 Best practice 1: Build Context-Specific Business Models

Effective business models are co-created with local stakeholders. Farmers, SMEs, cooperatives, and civil society actors help shape models that are practical, relevant, and socially accepted.

How to

- **Build on what exists.** Review local innovation projects, inventories (e.g. waste streams), regional strategies, and circular economy roadmaps.
- Conduct a **territorial analysis** using regional data, biomass mapping tools (e.g. Bioregions Facility, JRC Bioeconomy Dashboard).
- Identify strategically important **value chains** in your region and **engage stakeholders** along the entire value chain.
- Use **community mapping methods** to involve key stakeholders to identify and map resources, needs, and assets.
- **Validate regularly** organizing iteration sessions to refine the model with stakeholder feedback. Especially with consumers.

Key question for practitioners:

Who are the key actors in my region—and how can I meaningfully involve them in shaping this model?

What unique resources and value chains define my region—and how can they shape my business model?

Examples

- **Tuscany Region:** Developed short value chains rooted in local agricultural and forestry biomass (e.g. olive pruning, dairy waste). Models were co-designed with farmers and local processors and emphasized circularity, regional identity, and climate mitigation. Stakeholder feedback was integrated through structured dialogues and consultations,

ensuring the strategy reflected real market and environmental needs. The approach was highly place-sensitive, recognizing the fragmented landscape and existing agri-food sectors.

- **Delta Region:** Developed models tailored to the chemical and agri-food sectors, taking advantage of large ports, agricultural activity and industrial clusters. CBBB made an inventory of the potential existing in the region.
- **The Nitra Region:** Developed context-specific business models focused on waste management and agriculture, leveraging its rural profile and agricultural tradition. The PZO municipal consortium handles 15,000 tons of biowaste annually and operates a composting facility tailored to regional biomass types (e.g. grass, kitchen waste). Moreover, it created a regional bioeconomy platform to enable multi-actor dialogue. The Bioeconomy Cluster (BEC) conducted stakeholder mapping and engaged actors from over 50 institutions—including municipalities, local businesses, NGOs, and civil society—through co-creation workshops.
- **Western Macedonia Region:** The blueprint development was grounded in a series of participatory activities such as a Delphi-SWOT analysis involving regional experts and local stakeholders. SMEs, startups and farmers engaged through working groups.

4.1.2 Best Practice 2: Strengthen Value Chain Integration and Local Resource Valorisation

Well-integrated value chains that maximise the use of regional biomass and waste streams increase efficiency, resilience, and environmental performance.

How to

- **Map value chains** using supply chain analysis or tools to identify actors from input to end product.
- **Prioritize local**, renewable resources and minimize long-distance supply chains.
- **Identify the core resources** needed to create and deliver your value. These could be human (skilled labour), natural (biomass), financial, or technological.
- **Identify resource flows** working with waste management agencies, agri-coops, or forestry services to understand local material availability.
- **Build partnerships** connecting actors in different parts of the chain to improve coordination and reduce leakage.

Key question for practitioners:

What are the essential assets I need to deliver my solution and operate effectively?

How well are local actors connected across the value chain—and where are the missing links or inefficiencies?

Examples

- **Tuscany Region:** Developed circular value chains using local resources such as olive waste and winery by-products, promoting regional biomass utilization to reduce dependency on external inputs.
- **Western Macedonia Region:** Focused on integrating agri-food and forestry waste into new value chains, with an emphasis on technical feasibility and market access. The value chain approach is key to maximizing resource efficiency and minimizing waste.

- **Delta Region:** Highlighted short-term value chain solutions and strong sector integration, particularly in bio-based chemicals.

4.2 ENABLING ENVIRONMENT – FINANCE, POLICY, AND REPLICABILITY

A strong enabling environment ensures that innovations are not isolated but supported by strategic funding, aligned policies, and knowledge-sharing mechanisms. By promoting cross-regional learning, reinforcing local value chain integration, and aligning with financial and policy frameworks, regions can accelerate implementation, attract investment, and ensure that successful models are adaptable and replicable across diverse contexts.

4.2.1 Best Practice 3: Ensure Scalability and Flexibility Through Policy and Financial Support

Business models must be designed for scale and resilience. For this scope, it is important to navigate policy instruments and funding streams, and to adapt to changing frameworks.

How to

- **Ensure alignment** of your model with relevant policies, including regional strategies, the EU Green Deal, and local climate plans.
- **Secure a diverse funding mix** by combining local, national, and EU programmes (e.g., Horizon Europe, LIFE, regional RDP) to integrate both short- and long-term funding options.
- **Explore various ways to generate revenue**, such as direct sales, leasing, and services, while aligning pricing models with customer expectations and cash flow requirements.
- **Plan for scale-up by** using scaling tools or roadmaps (e.g., TRL/MRL levels) to structure your growth path, and invest in the capacity to attract funding to overcome critical funding gap (the Valley of Death).

Key questions for practitioners:

Does my business model have the financial and policy support needed to grow and adapt over time?

How will my business earn revenue—and what will customers be willing to pay for?

Examples

- **Tuscany Region:** Aligned innovation models with the EU Green Deal and utilized regional RDP funds to scale initiatives, ensuring compliance with environmental regulations and aligning with EU Green Deal objectives.
- **Delta Region:** Focused on "short-term solutions" with flexible design and multi-level funding, including innovation vouchers and the Just Transition Fund, to efficiently manage resources.

- **Western Macedonia Region:** Designed business models within the framework of NSRF 2021–2027 and Horizon Europe funding instruments to support regional innovation.

4.2.2 Best practice 4: Embed Circularity, Sustainability, and Social Impact in the Core Value Proposition

Business models must not only be sustainable but equitable. This means understanding who benefits, who bears the risks, and how environmental or social externalities are distributed across regions. This should be at the core of any business model—integrating circular design principles and low-carbon objectives throughout the value chain, from input sourcing to output management, considering disadvantage actor.

How to

- Set **clear environmental targets** (e.g., CO₂ reduction, zero waste, water reuse).
- Incorporate **life cycle thinking** into model development.
- **Emphasize a holistic approach** rather than focusing solely on environmental targets, as this comprehensive perspective provides a more accurate understanding of reality and supports scaling with truly sustainable goals.
- **Conduct impact assessments:** Apply environmental (e.g. LCA or carbon footprint tools) and social (e.g. SIA, equity mapping) tools during design.
- **Identify potential negative impacts and develop strategies to prevent or mitigate them.** This proactive approach ensures that sustainability efforts are balanced and credible, strengthening the enterprise’s long-term viability and social license to operate.
- **Communicate environmental, social and economic benefits clearly** in business pitches, funding applications, and policy engagements.
- **Use KPIs:** Define clear indicators for CO₂ reduction, land use, job creation, or community benefit.
- **Consult affected communities:** Especially in rural or marginalised areas, involve residents and end-users to avoid unintended consequences.

Key question for practitioners:

How does my business model reduce waste, emissions, and environmental harm across the entire value chain?

Does my business model consider and assess both positive and negative impacts?

Who benefits from this model—and are there risks of social, environmental or economic harm that I need to address?

Example

- **Tuscany Region:** Developed value chains based on local inputs and short loops, reducing environmental footprint -- Value chains based on local inputs and short loops to reduce footprint.

- **Western Macedonia Region:** Focused on valorising agricultural and forestry residues to reduce landfill dependency -- Valorisation of agricultural and forestry waste to reduce landfill use.
- **Delta Region:** Promoted business models that reduce emissions and help SMEs overcome technical barriers. It focused on reducing emissions and technical barriers for SMEs and incorporated sustainability KPIs and territorial data to guide equitable implementation strategies.
- **Nitra Region:** Addressed circularity in waste-based business models, converting bio-waste into compost and energy.
- **Northern Sweden:** Considered environmental impacts and inequality by integrating water management solutions to reduce negative local effects. Monitored water use and environmental footprint as part of the business model, mitigating potential negative effects.

4.3 INNOVATION AND MARKET DRIVEN APPROACHES

These best practices emphasize how innovation, technology, and market awareness drive resilient bio-based business models. They focus on aligning with real needs, managing complexity, and maintaining competitiveness through flexibility, environmental evaluation, and social equity.

4.3.1 Best practice 5: Leverage Innovation and Technology for Efficiency and Sustainability

Advanced technologies—such as biotechnology, digital monitoring, and automation—a high initial cost and thus an associated financial risk, but some measure allow fostering business models that leverage innovation, technology, and market alignment in a sustainable way.

How to

- **Integrate new technologies at small-scale and gradually.** Start with small-scale pilot projects to test new technologies before committing to large investments. Introduce technology gradually, spreading costs over time.
- **Digitise operations** using IoT, data analytics, or remote sensing to monitor resource use (e.g. water, waste, energy).
- **Involve knowledge institutions** for setting up innovation partnerships, internships, or pilot programs with research centres, universities, or tech providers to test biotechnologies, digital platforms, or smart sensors.
- **Conduct a thorough cost-benefit analysis** by comparing potential savings, revenue increases, or efficiencies against initial and ongoing technology integration costs.

Key question for practitioners:

Which technologies can increase my business model's efficiency—and who can help me apply them?

Examples

- **Northern Sweden:** Implemented water treatment and conservation technologies by installing meters and sensors to track water use and wastewater discharge. This improved efficiency and reduced environmental impact.
- **Tuscany Region:** Connected research and farming through AKIS and EIP-AGRI platforms to support adoption of sustainable technologies. Strong focus on integrating innovation ecosystems through universities, AKIS and EIP-AGRI platforms to support technological adoption in farming and processing.

- **Delta Region:** Emphasized the role of education and regional coordinating bodies (e.g. MNEXT, universities, regional development agencies) to support innovation through pilot testing and training.

4.3.2 Best practice 6: Adopt a Market-Driven Design Approach and Design for Dynamic Scenario Adaptability

Given rapid technological and market changes, business models must remain adaptable, requiring flexibility in their structure, operations, and long-term strategy. The strategic use of decision-making tools helps ensure alignment with market realities.

How to

- **Identify real demand** conducting market analysis, surveys, or stakeholder interviews to validate product-market fit.
- **Map how your product/service reaches customers.** Include both digital and physical delivery channels. Test for cost-efficiency and customer preference.
- **Identify and characterise your target customers.** Use segmentation techniques (e.g. personas, value-based grouping) to tailor the business model to specific user groups. Ensure the model delivers clear, measurable benefits to users—cost, sustainability, functionality.
- **Use scenario planning** for defining multiple future scenarios (policy shifts, climate events, tech disruption) and test model resilience.
- **Build in flexibility** creating modular models that allow for scale-up/down, pivoting, or relocation.
- **Use decision-making tools** by applying Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) or SWOT analysis to compare business model options.
- **Monitor early signals** by staying connected to policy, market, and tech trends via alerts, EU platforms, or innovation ecosystems.

Key questions for practitioners:

What real needs or gaps does my model address—and how attractive is it in the current market?

Who are my key customers and what specific needs or behaviours do they have?

How will my model respond to unexpected changes in policy, technology, or market dynamics?

Examples

- **Northern Sweden:** Used Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) tool to evaluate and prioritize business model alternatives for a biorefinery. The tool assessed cost, sustainability, and performance, enabling resource allocation aligned with market attractiveness and technical feasibility.
- **Western Macedonia Region:** Identified underutilized biomass and aligned models with niche markets to improve local value capture. Developed innovative approaches to both technology adoption and market access, with models focused on underutilized local biomass and new market segments.

5 BEST PRACTICES FOR GOVERNANCE MODEL DEVELOPMENT

Effective governance in regional bioeconomy strategies requires **multi-level structures** that are inclusive, aligned with policy frameworks, and supported by a coordinating body to ensure consistent communication and learning. Best practices highlight the importance of **transparent governance mechanisms**, fostering collaboration across local, regional, and national levels. Such structures facilitate coordination, enhance accountability, and strengthen the overall sustainability of bioeconomy initiatives. By increasing transparency and actively involving stakeholders in decision-making, these practices help ensure that strategies remain relevant, adaptive, and capable of addressing evolving challenges.

5.1 COLLABORATIVE AND INCLUSIVE MULTI-LEVEL GOVERNANCE STRUCTURES

Establishing coordinated systems that include local, regional, and national actors across sectors ensures broad ownership, accountability, and long-term viability.

5.1.1 Best Practice 1: Dedicated Coordinating Bodies to Support Multi-Actor Collaboration

Create dedicated structures or bodies (e.g., task forces, clusters, or liaison offices) that bring together public institutions, industry, academia, and civil society to manage implementation and keep bioeconomy strategies on track.

How to

- **Identify existing platforms** or consortia that can evolve into governance hubs.
- **Identify key actors and define clear roles** for coordination, reporting, and support functions.
- **Secure stable structure** to support coordination over time.

Key questions for practitioners:

How can I ensure continuity, coordination, and accountability across sectors?

What kind of structure could facilitate multi-actor collaboration?

Examples

- **Delta Region:** The Circular Biobased Delta (CBBDD) acted as a triple-helix coordination platform. This helped maintain stakeholder alignment and led to concrete policy recommendations.
- **Nitra Region:** With the Bioeconomy Cluster (BEC), which was established in 2015 to act as a coordinating and convening body across public and private sectors, the Region ensures alignment with local and national policies.
- **Western Macedonia:** A Policy Development Task Force was formed to manage policy alignment and implementation coordination.

5.1.2 Best Practice 2: Ensuring Effective Strategy Implementation with Clear Governance Structure

Clearly assigning roles and responsibilities with defined timelines helps prevent fragmentation and ensures the effective operationalization of strategies.

How to

- Ensure representation from all sectors using a **quadruple helix model**—public, private, research, civil society.
- **Co-develop governance priorities** and frameworks using co-creation workshops.
- Develop **implementation roadmaps** with defined responsibilities and milestones across governance levels.
- **Assign responsibilities** at municipal, regional, and national levels, ensuring clear accountability.
- Link governance roles to **available financial resources** to ensure capacity for execution.
- **Regularly review and adjust roles** as necessary to adapt to emerging needs or challenges.

Key questions for practitioners:

Are roles clearly defined, and are institutions equipped to carry them out effectively?

Are my governance frameworks shaped by diverse voices and grounded in real local dynamics?

Examples

- **Western Macedonia Region:** Included clear timelines and task distribution within the implementation framework, ensuring accountability at all levels.
- **Normandy Region:** Coordinated policy efforts through regional authorities and inter-regional platforms, ensuring alignment across governance levels.
- **Northern Sweden:** Used co-creation workshops to refine and validate governance models. Stakeholder input shaped priorities in the final blueprint.
- **Tuscany:** Actively included farmers, companies, and public actors in the blueprint's development, facilitating cross-sector dialogue.
- **Nitra:** Quadruple helix approach strengthened policy dialogue through open feedback loops.

5.2 POLICY ALIGNMENT AND TRANSPARENT GOVERNANCE

Connecting strategies to broader policy goals is important for ensuring coherence among actors boosts impact, legitimacy, and funding opportunities. Additionally, continuous monitoring and transparent governance enhance accountability and enable effective, adaptive management.

5.2.1 Best Practice 3: Align Governance with Regional, National, and EU Frameworks

Connecting local strategies to broader agendas (e.g., EU Green Deal, Circular Economy Action Plan) enhances policy consistency and access to funding.

How to

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- **Map overlapping goals** between the bioeconomy strategy and other frameworks.
- **Engage national ministries or EU platforms in advisory roles and Join European clusters and platforms:** e.g. BIOEAST, ERRIN, Vanguard Initiative, CBE JU
- **Develop formal mechanisms for policy dialogue**, such as inter-agency working groups, to ensure continuous alignment and feedback.

Key questions for practitioners:

How does our governance framework connect with broader policy objectives at all levels?

Examples

- **Tuscany:** Aligned with the EU Green Deal and regional climate targets to promote green jobs and sustainability.
- **Northern Sweden:** Integrated bioeconomy strategy with national forestry and climate priorities.
- **Delta Region:** Embedded the strategy within national circular economy policy and Just Transition Fund programmes.
- **Western Macedonia Region:** Through Bioeconomy and Environment Cluster of Western Macedonia-CluBE, and participating in EU knowledge networks (e.g. CBE JU, BIOEAST), the Region fostered cross-regional learning

5.2.2 Best Practice 4: Establish Monitoring and Evaluation Systems for Transparent Governance

Robust data collection and sharing mechanisms help track progress, support evidence-based adjustments, and build trust among stakeholders.

→ How to

- **Create public dashboards or reports** to share results and trends.
- **Establish advisory committees** or task forces that regularly convene to discuss challenges, opportunities, and progress.
- **Document your process** using templates (e.g. business model canvas, KPI dashboards) that others can adapt.
- **Use indicators (KPIs)** to track progress.
- Organize or **join peer-learning formats** such as study visits, twinning schemes, or webinars can facilitate real exchange.

Key questions for practitioners:

Are we tracking the right indicators and sharing information transparently with all stakeholders?

Examples

- **Delta Region:** Used SMART KPIs and professional dashboards to guide strategic decisions and enhance transparency.

6 SUMMARY OF RECOMMENDATIONS AND IMPLEMENTATION GUIDELINES

The analysis of the six pilot regions revealed several critical insights that underpin successful regional bioeconomy strategies. These findings highlight essential factors such as stakeholder engagement, capacity building, context-specific business models, integrated circularity and equity, effective governance, and the importance of data-driven monitoring. Together, they provide a foundation for developing replicable best practices while emphasizing the need for tailored approaches to local contexts and policy environments.

In summary, the main insights emerging from the analysis are:

- **Stakeholder Engagement is Foundational:** Early, inclusive, and structured engagement of actors across the quadruple helix (public, private, academia, civil society) is a critical enabler for strategy ownership and effective implementation.
- **Capacity Building and Awareness-Raising Ensure Long-Term Viability:** Training programs, knowledge-sharing platforms, and awareness campaigns proved essential in empowering local actors and fostering long-term commitment.
- **Business Models Must Be Context-Specific and Market-Aligned:** Successful models are deeply rooted in regional value chains, designed to valorize local biomass, and structured to address specific market demands.
- **Circularity and Equity Must Be Embedded from the Start:** The best-performing business models integrated life-cycle thinking, environmental KPIs, and social impact considerations, ensuring benefits are equitably distributed and risks mitigated.
- **Governance Requires Clear Roles and Policy Coherence:** Functional governance frameworks included coordinating bodies, formalized responsibilities, and alignment with national and EU strategies, boosting legitimacy and funding access.
- **Data Systems and Monitoring are Underutilized but Crucial:** Where present, transparent data collection and performance monitoring systems (e.g., KPIs, dashboards) supported strategic adaptation and accountability.

Overall, the practices show high replicability potential but require tailored adaptations to regional contexts and policy frameworks.

7 CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable provides a comprehensive overview of actionable best practices for supporting regional bioeconomy transitions. The lessons learned from the six pilot regions highlight the importance of combining inclusive processes, context-aware solutions, and enabling governance mechanisms.

The diversity of regional approaches demonstrates that there is no one-size-fits-all model. However, the core principles — stakeholder co-creation, local value chain integration, circularity, market orientation, and transparent governance — can serve as universal anchors for strategy development.

For regions aiming to develop or strengthen their bioeconomy ecosystems, these guidelines offer a practical reference to design blueprints that are robust, socially responsive, and environmentally sustainable. The recommendations provided serve not only as a toolkit for action but also as a foundation for continuous learning and cross-regional collaboration.

